

Local Self Government in Uzbekistan: The functioning of *Mahalla*'s Citizens**Assemblies****Dr. Govind Kumar Inakhiya**

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6972094

Pages: 01-11

Vol 5, Issue 1 (Jan-Jun 2022)

Abstract

One of the most significant political events of the final decade of the 20th century was the dissolution of the USSR in 1991, which allowed for greater democratic rights and liberalism by fundamentally altering the member republics' basic integrity. In the aftermath of the dissolution of the erstwhile Soviet Union, the government of Uzbekistan initiated economic and political reforms on a large scale. In its agenda of political reforms, attempts were made to establish a multi-party system based on the liberal democratic model of the political system. After getting independence, Uzbekistan adopted its own Constitution in 1992 which led to the foundation of various political institutions. The Constitution of the republic declared Uzbekistan democratic and secular. The republic has adopted the presidential form of government with the unitary type of political system.

On 2nd September 1993, the Government of Uzbekistan passed a law on Local Public Administration, and “that established structure and system of local government in the country. According to law structure of local government consist of two: i. the system of local state administration, and ii. the local self-government. The further local governments of Uzbekistan are subdivided into regional, district, and city administration” (Bektemirov and Rahimov, 2002:488).

In this paper, an attempt has been made to analyze the functioning of local self-government institutions in the republic. Also, try to explore constitutional practices and how the practices operate. What extent the demand for decentralization and strengthening of local self-government institutions and provide more space to *Mahalla* Citizens Assemblies which would have more influence over decision-making?

The paper is mainly divided into three sections: Section I deals with the ‘Concept of Local Self Governance’ and the evolution of ‘Local Self-governance in Uzbekistan before

independence’, Section II, ‘Local Self-governance in Uzbekistan post-independence’, and with special reference to *Mahalla* Citizen Assembly and Section III ‘The Modern Day *Mahalla* as an Instrument of State Administration’

Keywords: *Mohalla, Self-Governance, Local Public Administration, Tsarist and Soviet Period*

Local Self Government

Government Functioning is broadly categorized into three levels: National, State, and Local. Local Self-Government, closely tied with the concept of democratic decentralization, is the structure of local governance that mainly looks after small areas like village, town, and urban cities. The functioning of the structures depends on local revenues and taxes generated by these structures through elected and nominated members. It is also considered a form of self-organization among local people that fosters the formation of civil society. The role of local government institutions is to create better living conditions for the rural people. It is the process of a sense of responsibility for solving local problems through the involvement of local people. It is also a mechanism to control the activities of government by local people.

These institutions are very important in terms of reducing social tension, resolving conflict in a better way, promoting social, and economic development of the local area, create a sustainable environment in the area.

Local self-government is working with the constitutional provisions of the respective countries, such as the European Charter on Local Self Government, Great Britain, Australia, Germany, Switzerland, USA, and 73rd & 74th Constitutional Amendment act in India. Worldwide practices of local self-governance institutions have provided a safe pass to the newly independent countries from the Soviet Union, Uzbekistan also initiated the process with the constitutional provisions and made effort to an establish local self-government institutions for the fulfil the need of the local people of the country

Administrative and Territorial Structure of the Uzbek Government

The Uzbek constitution structures the territorial administration into four tiers (levels); the republican (first tier), the province (*Viloyat*, Second tier)), and the district (*Tumans*, third tier). After the third tier of territorial administration, both self-governance systems and state hierarchies have many local government entities operating within them. Cities with district subordination, towns, and villages are all regarded as local self-government and state structures

in Uzbekistan. The *Mahallas* committee of self-governing citizen assemblies at the local level is regarded as the fourth-tier administrative organisation. These *Mahallas* have been established to run the administration of villages and settlements in the towns. Since independence, the local self-government institutions have been playing a vital role in district and village administration. The so-called “*Mahalla*” institute occupies a highly important place in Uzbek society. This is a kind of public self-government. The “*Mahalla*” resolves a number of problems related to the social aspects of life inside town and blocks or *kishlaks*.

***Mahalla* During the Tsarist and Soviet Period**

During the Tsarist period, the *Mahalla* was the basic unit of the administration, and the internal mechanism of administrative machinery was mainly focused on interaction with the local *Mahalla* population. During the Soviet period, the *Mahalla* unit has been developed as self local governing residential association. During the Soviet period, the *Mahalla* was headed by the chairperson and called *aksaqal*, the appointment of the *aksaqal* was controlled by the local party apparatus. The *aksaqal* for the decision instead of the formal advisor, he was depended on a committee and the committee's job was to advise him. There were certain functions also managed by some different committees in the *Mahalla*. The ambiance of the *Mahalla* committee looks like soviet offices, “decorated with Soviet symbols, icons, and graced portraits of soviet leaders” (Seiple 2005:250-251).

After the nationalizing of economic activities in the Soviet Union, the next step has been initiated which was the devolution of the state power into nongovernmental hands. In the twentieth Party Congress of 1956 and Party Program of the Nineteen Sixty, a resolution was passed for the regulation of the devolution powers of the state and the matter of getting these powers done through social association (Sharlet 2007:3-4).

For the devolution process, the soviet system made out three distinct categories of social connections, i. Social movement organization, ii. Social association, and iii. Social self-organization.

In Uzbekistan after independence trade union and Red Cross have highlighted four distinct elements such as they give voluntary memberships, own charter for the functioning, property and self-government for the social organizations.

Another category is a social movement organization, the soviet peace committee, a kind of more informal setup with the less membership. During the Soviet era all movements never felt financial crunches due to state funding.

In central Asian countries social self-governing organisation namely *Mahalla*, with the composition of *Druziny*, *Domovye*, *Ulichnye* and *Kvartalye Komitey* (Residential committees), *Selskomy* (Agriculture Committee) included parents committee for schools. These SSGOs are responsible for defending citizens' rights to take part in controlling the government and society. SSGOs of CARs enjoy quasi-governmental powers (Sievers 2002: 115). The formation of the SSGOs decrees state agencies, unlike social organisations, CARs SSGOs do not have paid employees or legal standing.

During the Soviet era most of the Soviet Social Association enjoyed prominent in the relationship with the state. The Soviet system had an agreement with these organisations, democratically promoted them and granted the authority to retain assets in trust and carry out fiduciary duties. A more effective organisation with essentially the same fiduciary obligations was intended for social associations. SSGOs were most frequently to channel the interests of isolated employment groups or a local community.

In the time of the Soviet era, in Uzbekistan apartment complexes were not considered as a *Mahalla*. The status of apartment complexes under the residential SSGOs is based on Siberia or Georgia model. The size of the residential committee of the *Mahallas* is very time and space. It can be a few dozen people, a single family with large numbers of members, several hundred to thousands. The comparison of modern *Mahalla* with the traditional *Mahallas* the size more or less contains 2000 individuals (Sievers 2002:118).

There are some pieces of evidence of the pre-Tsarist *Mahalla* system and it compared with the Soviet era, During the Soviet era, the citizens of the land anticipated essentially nothing in the way of public amenities from the state. *Mahalla* residents expected more facilities from the government in various forms such as demand for good schools, medical facilities, potable water, control on crime with the state intervention.

Post-Soviet *Mahalla*'s Citizens Assemblies in Uzbekistan

After the independence of Uzbekistan, the structure of local self-government has got great importance. The *Mahalla* system continues in Uzbekistan, some new additions it has retained traditional functions as well. Modern *Mahalla* systems is a combination of both state

administration and local self-government. The *Mahalla* systems serve below the district level and control. In common words, it is called neighbourhood assemblies.

There are two different meanings of *Mahalla*:

1. It alludes to a loosely organised solidarity network that all customarily grounded people belong to. (Socio- Anthropological sense)
2. Following independence, it was given legal stature as a body for citizen self-government, in the social sphere role of it was assigned to paid official (Legal– Administrative sense) (Stevens 2002:282).

During the tsarist as well as soviet era *Mahalla* never got legal status, but after the independence, it has recognized through the constitution of Uzbekistan, article 105 of the 1992 constitution of Uzbekistan refers to *Mahalla*, and recognized as a part of local government administration.

As per time and space, needs and local requirements Government of Uzbekistan has passed a number of legislations about the new responsibilities to the *Mahalla*. Other Central Asian countries such as Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan have similar local self government and got legal status like Uzbekistan. “According to official figures, by 2006 Uzbekistan had over 8,000 registered *mahallas*, on an average, there are about 2500-3000 people living in each *Mahalla*” (UNDP 2006).

***Mahalla’s* Citizens Assemblies: Composition and Structure (authorities and other officials)**

After the enactment of the constitution, *Mahalla* got constitutional status through article -105 (Constitution of Uzbekistan 1992:). In April 1999 Government of Uzbekistan has introduced the law on “Community Self–Government” and same time other legislation. Additionally, the entire *Mahalla* community functions as a form of citizen assembly. According to this law, every Uzbek citizen is a member of at least one of these citizens' assemblies. At the top hierarchy of *Mahalla* constitute a committee consisting of 15 members called as *Kengash*. The chairman of *Kengash* called as *Oqsoqol*, the Seceretary of *Kengash* called as *Kotib*. There are other advisors for some specific matters in the *Kengash*. These advisors often “correspond to the state ministerial functions as an advisor on religion, for the women’s committee, for health etc. Also there are some advisors for the traditional function like wedding planning and

coordination in various ceremonies in locality” (Steven 2005: 285). Modern time some positions of officer are created in *Mahalla* specially advisor of education and neighbourhood guardian.

Term and Conditions for *Mahalla*'s Citizens Assemblies Authorities

The Government of Uzbekistan has passed a law on ‘Citizens Self Government Institutions’, article -20 of the law refers to the election process of the *Mahalla* Chairman (*Oqsoqol*), the term of the *Oqsoqol*, two years six months, and the election is based on getting one half the votes cast and with the approval of the appropriate district or city *Hokim*. The process of the election of *Oqsoqol* and *Kengash* was more and less based on according the law as per government officials. The membership of the *Mahalla* committee to be provided all 18 years aged persons.

For the conducting elections of the *Oqsoqol* and *Kengash*, responsibility given to the electoral commission (Nominating Committee), EC divides the *Mahalla*'s in to various sectors (mostly in blocks or streets, like in India Wards in Panchayats). From each sector will choose a representative to participate in the general assembly. The representative of the sectors find by the EC more or less are some kinds of the political affiliation or some kinds of the local leaders are recognised. Further, a district *Mahalla* foundation director and an *Oqsoqol* have an interview role. The entire exercise of the election in the observation of the official of the district or city *Hokimiyat*. The role of the official from the district *Hokimiyat* is to screening of the candidates, to check criminal record, terrorist associations and religious opposition of the candidate nominated by the EC.

The Power and Functions of *Mahalla*'s Citizens Assemblies.

According to 1999 ‘law on community self-government, citizen assemblies in villages, *shlaks*, auls and mahallas are mainly responsible for the following activities and functions’ (Bektemirov and Rahimov, 2002: 486-487):

1. The *Mahalla* is responsible for electing both the committee chairman and committee members. *Mahalla* chooses a chairman and members of the commission from the assembly area so that they can participate in activities related to the assembly and examine the reports that they provide on a quarterly basis.

1. *Mahalla* elects and audits of administrative commission.
2. All actions plan and expenditures of the community self-governments are approved by the *Mahalla*.

3. *Mahalla* plays an important role in the carrying out of both national legislation and orders issued by local governments at the community level.
4. *Mahalla*, for the presidential, parliamentary and local council elections' representative of district election committee.
5. *Mahalla* has the authority to review reports on matters that fall under the purview of community self-government that are submitted by the heads of the district, city, and regional *Hokimiyats*.
6. These reports are then sent to the regional Tashkent *Hokimiyats*, which file them and regulate whether or not the applications of citizens are fulfilled; *Mahalla* serve as mediators in the correspondence between citizen assemblies on these reports.
7. 8. Participation in the process of generating funds for one's own local self-government and in the ownership, management, and sale of local government property;
8. Role in controlling expenditures;
9. Collects voluntary financial contributions for the area to better public spaces or to aid low-income families in the maintenance and repair of their homes
10. Makes a decision regarding the voluntary pooling of funds from businesses and individuals for the purpose of the development of the community's social infrastructure;
11. *Mahalla* sends the representative in land and plots allotments.

Financial Activities of *Mahalla*

Local unit *Mahalla*'s Citizens Assemblies are empowered to generate own resources for the economic activities at local level. New laws and legislation have made some arrangement about the *Mahalla*'s Citizens Assemblies and permitted them to established industrial enterprises, shops and canteens, which helps in *Mahalla* funds. for the routine works *Hokimiyats* gives some financial support.

Role of *Mahalla* in Social Reforms

In the promotion of folk customs and traditions, *Mahalla* playing a vital role. It has important in providing historical and spiritual values, and in disseminating cultural and educational activities among the *Mahallas*. Also, provide social and economic facilities to the local residents of respective *Mahallas*. There are foundations of the *Mahalla*'s for all these activities. *Mahalla* Foundation organizes different events and publishes the *Mahalla* newspaper.

The following activities are directed by the foundation:

- i. Role of the foundation to improve the activities of local *Mahalla* committees nationwide.
- ii. Foundations are involved in the social protection of poor families, disabled people and children of the local area.
- iii. Also promoting humanism, mutual understanding, mercy, and a healthy relationship with the neighbors.

The government's objectives have changed from providing universal social protection to supporting the most disadvantaged demographic groups, in addition to all these community-based assistance programmes. The motive of social assistance is to identify needy people and reduce administrative expenses such as the special *Mahalla* commission paying benefits to unemployed mothers of children under two. In this context December 1996, the Presidential Decree on the increase of Material Support for children.

This decree has provided more space to families with children it is one of the largest social programs in Uzbekistan in terms of expenditure and beneficiaries, approximately 6.3 percent of national budget expenses are assigned to this program. Again, in January 1999, the Presidential Decree was issued, and that mainly related to increasing the role of community self-governments in providing target social assistance.

The best part of the target social assistance is transferred to the *Mahalla* to subsidize public facilities and services to the poor and low-income families. But all these efforts have been made by the local *Mahalla* committee through local administrative units. But more responsibilities to the local administration have transferred in over the bureaucratization of *Mahalla* committee activities.

The Modern-Day *Mahalla* as an Instrument of State Administration:

The increasing role of the *Mahalla* in various spheres of individual of the localities within the realm of social policy, both as a tool of state administration and in its more traditional capacities and functions. *Mahalla* is distributing social assistance payments, raising school-age children, reproduction, health and family planning, handle the request for divorce and complaints related to domestic violence.

National governments time to time get help in social policy related matter from the local *Mahalla* mechanism in terms of effective implementation of programs related to social

policy, program likewise – minority education, pension etc. all these programs and schemes are delegated to the *Mahallas* and other organs of local governments by the motivational and provincial governments. More advanced role of the *Mahalla* in helping government and Civil society institutions. There are NGOs in Uzbekistan are cooperating in various sectors with the *Mahalla* like USAID, Red Apple Program and Swiss Water Project. At local level schools *Mahalla*'s educational advisors are active in monitoring the absenteeism of teachers and students. *Mahalla*'s educational advisors are helping in encouraging enrolment, and consultation with parents' social education programs.

Grey Areas of the Functioning of *Mahalla*

There are some instances related to malpractices in the function of the *Mahalla* reported such as the election of *Mahalla* is merely a rubber-stamp. The candidates for the *Mahalla* offered by the District *Hokim*, show the undemocratic process in the appointments and elections of the *Mahalla* committees, elections are not free from the upper hands.

In the appointment of *Oqsoqols*, (Fireman) at *Mahalla* level, role of district *Hokim* is very *controversial*. Without waiting their tenure and term and conditions he appoints new *Oqsoqols* at *Mahalla*. In the functioning of *Mahalla*, mall practices have been reported, deviation from state policy on providng various welfare assistance, rule and law-breaking practices, officer avoid the legal implications of an investigation. The common practice found in the removal of the *Oqsoqols*. The *Oqsoqols* resign from the post just simply on the request of the district *Hokim*.

The election of the new chairman on the basis of a meeting of the representative, no such announcement of the meeting where the 'Law on Citizens' Self-Government allows for voting that is open or secret, direct or through representatives. Though voting by the open meeting of representatives remains the norm' (Bektemirov and Rahimov, 2002:483).

Conclusion

Despite all propaganda about introduction of decentralization in the name of *Mahalla* citizens assemblies and committees. At the end we can say that the administrative structure of Uzbekistan is still centralized and highly politicized. In this regard one can say that local self-government and decision-making institutions are still not free in the republic. Repeated amendments and reforms are the sign of the change and development. Still enough has to be done. The political culture of the country needs to be changed. It is significant to understand

that Uzbekistan is passing through transition period. One can look forward to deepening of reforms in the country.

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